

DEVELOPMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY OF TÜRKIYE- UZBEKISTAN FOREIGN TRADE

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Foreign trade activities are extremely important for the economic development of countries. It is possible to say that increases in foreign trade revenues are of great importance, especially in terms of increasing gross national product. Foreign trade activities directly affect economic growth both by causing increases in production volume due to increases in demand for national goods and services and by redirecting the income obtained as a result of export activities to production. In addition, it is possible to say that foreign trade activities have a positive impact on employment rates, especially in developing countries with young populations. In addition, foreign trade activities have significant effects on exchange rates and inflation. Increasing foreign trade activities, especially export revenues, which have such significant macroeconomic effects, is of great importance for two developing countries, Türkiye and Uzbekistan. Aware of this importance, the two countries are demonstrating a tendency to increase their mutual trade. This study provides information on the development of foreign trade between Turkey and Uzbekistan over the years and the sustainability of trade between the two countries.

Keywords: Foreign Trade, Sustainability, Türkiye, Uzbekistan

INTRODUCTION

It's safe to say that foreign trade activities are extremely important from an economic perspective. No country possesses all the factors of production. For this reason, even if some of the production factors needed for production activities can be supplied within the country, some of them must be supplied from other countries. This makes foreign trade activities essential. In this context, it's safe to say that foreign trade transactions are crucial for both the implementation and continuity of national production activities. Turkey's production policy underwent a significant change and transformation after 1980. From that date on, instead of an economic policy based on import substitution and partially closed to foreign trade, Turkey adopted an open economic policy, primarily focused on exports. As stated earlier, unlike other countries, Turkey does not have all the production factors and therefore has to import some of the raw materials and intermediate goods needed for production. Thanks to this policy change, and in line with global developments, the movement of goods, services, and capital has been significantly liberalized, and numerous legal regulations have been implemented to this end. Furthermore, despite the fragility of the country's economic structure, the principle of open economic management has never been abandoned [1]. Thanks to this resolute stance, an open economic structure and foreign trade activities have significantly contributed to the country's economy. It's safe to say that foreign trade activities, especially exports, are extremely important from an

economic perspective. Thanks to export revenues, new investments can be planned, employment volume can increase, production volume can increase, inflation rate can decrease and exchange rates can decline. Particularly for countries like Turkey, which are dependent on imported inputs, declines in exchange rates contribute to a significant improvement in inflation rates because they translate into lower input costs. Supporting and increasing foreign trade, which is so economically important, through various means is crucial for building a strong economic structure. Aware of this reality, Türkiye is taking the necessary measures and undertaking significant initiatives to increase its foreign trade activities. In this context, it is striving to develop its trade activities by land and sea with many countries, particularly in the region, and globally. One of the countries with which Turkey is eager to engage and develop commercial activities is Uzbekistan, a friendly nation. In recent years, Uzbekistan's production volume has increased and it is experiencing a rapid growth process. It is possible to say that the country's natural resources, mines and young population, in other words its human resources, have an impact on this rapid development in production volume. Furthermore, effective evaluation of these resources is extremely important for the development of the country's economy. In this context, export revenues are also extremely important for Uzbekistan. The mutual development of foreign trade activities between the two countries, which share strong historical, cultural, and social ties, will benefit both countries economically. Based on this reality, it is useful to first reveal the development of trade relations between Türkiye and Uzbekistan, to identify existing problems in the next stage, and finally to focus on the measures that need to be taken to develop

Years	Türkiye's Imports from Uzbekistan	Türkiye's Exports to Uzbekistan	Trade Balance between Türkiye and Uzbekistan	Foreign Trade Total
2001	36.045	89.725	53.680	125.770
2002	75.342	93.735	18.393	169.077
2003	99.462	138.422	38.960	237.884
2004	178.671	145.226	-33.445	323.897
2005	261.466	151.071	-110.395	412.537
2006	415.841	175.995	-239.846	591.836
2007	613.810	225.612	-388.198	839.422
2008	580.810	337.130	-243.680	917.940
2009	413.079	279.964	-133.115	693.043
2010	861.373	282.666	-578.707	1.144.039
2011	939.882	354.490	-585.392	1.294.372
2012	813.287	449.884	-363.403	1.263.171
2013	853.058	624.482	-228.576	1.477.540
2014	846.432	650.355	-196.077	1.496.787
2015	711.555	488.652	-222.903	1.200.207
2016	709.292	533.322	-175.970	1.242.614
2017	823.275	680.104	-143.171	1.503.379
2018	795.545	951.458	155.913	1.747.003
2019	1.140.193	1.232.288	92.095	2.372.481
2020	969.984	1.154.334	184.350	2.124.318
2021	1.800.044	1.841.893	41.849	3.641.937

2022	1.682.528	1.877.915	195.387	3.560.443
2023	1.209.313	1.872.528	663.215	3.081.841
2024	1.134.188	2.228.215	1.094.027	3.362.403
2025*	608.719	1.120.193	511.474	1.728.912

trade between the two countries.

1. DEVELOPMENT OF TURKIYE-UZBEKISTAN FOREIGN TRADE

Uzbekistan is one of the important countries with which Turkey engages in trade. It is seen that countries have complementary characteristics in foreign trade in terms of their potential due to their natural resources and strategic importance. With this, this existing potential in the economic and commercial fields has not been fully utilized, but it is expected that over time the existing obstacles will disappear and the trade relations between the two countries will increase [2]. In line with this expectation, a number of mutual initiatives have been taken in the two countries and studies have been carried out on what measures should be taken to increase trade between the two countries. It is a well-known fact that Uzbekistan has experienced rapid economic growth since gaining independence, and that this growth has accelerated in recent years. In light of this information, it is useful to examine the development of foreign trade between the two countries.

**Table 1. Türkiye-Uzbekistan Foreign Trade
(Thousand Dollars)**

Source: Trademap, (Access Date: 17.09.2025)

https://www.trademap.org/Bilateral_TS.aspx?nvpm=1%7c792%7c%7c860%7c%7cTOTAL%7c%7c%7c2%7c1%7c1%7c2%7c2%7c1%7c1%7c1%7c1%7c1

* 2025 data is from TÜİK (Turkish Statistical Institute) and was published as of August 28, 2025.

TÜİK, (Accessed: September 17, 2025)

<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Kategori/GetKategori?p=dis-ticaret-104&dil=1>

An examination of the development of foreign trade between Turkey and Uzbekistan over the years reveals that Turkey's imports from Uzbekistan have fluctuated over the years. However, it is possible to say that the general trend is upward. Since the final data for 2025 has not yet been obtained, evaluations are made as of 2024. In the period under review, Turkey's imports from Uzbekistan reached their highest level in 2021. However, what is interesting here is that the import level, which was approximately \$970 million the previous year, increased by 85% in the following year, reaching \$1.8 billion in 2021. In 2021, approximately 80% of our imports consisted of "cotton, cotton yarn, and cotton fabrics" and "copper and copper articles." Approximately 55% of the \$830 million increase in our imports in 2021 was due to the increase in imports of "cotton yarn" and "refined copper and crude copper alloys"[3]. In addition, of the total \$1.8 billion imports from Uzbekistan in 2021, \$936.5 million consisted of copper and copper-made goods, while \$497.9 million consisted of cotton. As of the period under review, it is possible to say that Turkey's imports from Uzbekistan were mainly based on these two products [4]. Between 2001 and 2025, Turkey's imports from Uzbekistan reached their highest level in

2021 and then showed a continuous decline, reaching approximately \$1.68 billion in 2022, \$1.21 billion in 2023, and \$1.13 billion in 2024. These data indicate a significant decline of approximately \$666 million in Turkey's imports from Uzbekistan over the last three years.

Source: Prepared by me using the data in Table 1.

Turkey's exports to Uzbekistan, on the other hand, have developed more evenly and have increased continuously except for the years 2005, 2009, 2015, 2020, and 2023. The most notable development in Turkey's exports to Uzbekistan is seen in 2024. Turkey's revenue from exports to Uzbekistan, which reached approximately \$1.87 billion in 2023, reached approximately \$2.23 billion the following year, 2024. These data reveal a 19% increase in Turkey's export revenues from Uzbekistan. It is observed that products from the chemical substances and products and machinery and parts sectors come to the fore in exports to Uzbekistan. As of 2024, of the \$2.2 billion in export revenue generated by Uzbekistan, approximately \$362.2 million came from sales of chemicals and chemical products, and \$336.4 million from sales of machinery and components. The main increase in export revenues came from sales of products from the ready-made clothing sector. Export revenue from the sale of products from the ready-made clothing and apparel sector was approximately \$40.9 million in 2023, but this figure increased by 260.9% the following year, 2024, reaching approximately \$147.8 million. These data clearly reveal how rapidly export revenues, especially in the ready-made clothing and apparel sector, have increased. In addition, significant revenues are generated from the sales of products belonging to the air conditioning industry, electrical and electronics industry, and textile and raw materials industry [5]. As of the examined period of 2001-2025, it is seen that Turkey's exports to Uzbekistan have gained momentum in recent years and reached its highest value in 2024, and as of 2024, Turkey's revenue from exports to Uzbekistan is approximately 2.23 billion dollars. However, the real increase in export revenues occurred after 2020. It is seen that export revenues, which were 1.15 billion dollars as of 2020, were realized as approximately 1.84 billion

dollars in 2021 and 1.87 billion dollars in the next two years, and then increased to approximately 2.23 billion dollars in 2024. It is possible to say that the real break in this rise occurred in 2021, with an increase of approximately 687 million dollars, and that there was an increase of approximately 100% in 2024 compared to 2020.

2. CURRENT PROBLEMS RELATING TO TRADE ACTIVITIES BETWEEN TURKEY AND UZBEKISTAN

There is a significant trade potential between Türkiye and Uzbekistan, and accordingly, commercial activities between the two countries are developing rapidly. However, these developments in foreign trade activities and increases in trade volume are behind the current potential. Uzbekistan possesses the precious minerals, cotton and cotton yarn, mineral fuels, and chemical oils that Turkey needs for its production processes, and these products account for a significant share of the country's exports. Uzbekistan's imports, however, are primarily boilers and machinery, motor vehicles, and iron and steel products [6]. Uzbekistan also possesses significant natural gas and oil reserves. In this context, Türkiye needs the natural resources and products of Uzbekistan, and Uzbekistan needs the products produced in Türkiye or owned by Turkey. More clearly, while Türkiye exports industrial products and technology, it imports raw materials and agricultural products from Uzbekistan. In this respect, it is possible to say that the production structures of the two countries are complementary to each other and accordingly the trade between the two countries is developing in a balanced way [7]. However, it is possible to say that there are some obstacles to the effective exploitation of the existing trade potential between the two countries. One of the most important of these obstacles is the geographical location of the countries. There is a distance of 4000-4500 kilometers between the two countries. This distance poses a significant obstacle to the effective conduct of commercial activities. Because a significant transportation expense arises when moving commercial goods from one country to another, this causes a significant increase in trade costs and therefore a decrease in profits.

One of the most important elements of international trade is the customs clearance process for traded goods. Customs procedures are of great importance for the protection of national economies and consumers. Customs regulations determine the export and import conditions of products [8]. One of the obstacles that cause trade between the two countries to be limited is that customs procedures take longer than necessary, which causes time losses for businesses. The examination and testing processes of standard documents for goods imported by Uzbekistan take a long time, which causes business people in Turkey to be unable to fulfill their export commitments on time. Furthermore, import transactions in Uzbekistan can be suspended for a certain period due to exceeding import quotas or similar reasons. In addition, the long and costly process of obtaining an invitation from a company in Uzbekistan to obtain a visa for commercial activities poses an obstacle for entrepreneurs from Turkey who want to come to Uzbekistan and invest. This, in turn, hinders the development of commercial and economic relations between Turkey and Uzbekistan. Additionally, tax audits are conducted frequently and take a long time in Uzbekistan. During the tax audit process, some sections of businesses or factories are closed and production activities are stopped, which causes the production process to be interrupted [9]. This situation is undesirable for foreign trade. Another significant factor contributing to the limited trade between Turkey and Uzbekistan is the economic model

Uzbekistan was forced to implement for a time, even after its declaration of independence. Uzbekistan gained independence after the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, but for many years continued to follow a centrally planned economic model. This limited the country's economic development and prevented it from fully integrating into international trade networks [7]. This has caused trade relations between Türkiye and Uzbekistan to be below their potential level. In addition, the political tensions between the two countries in the past for various reasons and the resulting crisis in political relations have also negatively affected the trade between the two countries, and therefore, Turkey-Uzbekistan economic relations have not reached their potential level.

3. MEASURES TO BE TAKEN TO SOLVE TRADE PROBLEMS BETWEEN TURKEY AND UZBEKISTAN

In order to develop trade relations between Türkiye and Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take a series of measures and carry out some reforms. A Free Trade Agreement (FTA) to be drawn up within this scope will enable the reduction or elimination of trade barriers in order to increase trade between the party countries. A potential Free Trade Agreement between Uzbekistan and Turkey could contribute to a significant increase in trade volume between the two countries. Within the scope of the Free Trade Agreement, reducing or completely eliminating customs tariffs can reduce trade costs and enable products to be sold at more competitive prices in both countries. In addition, reducing customs tariffs within the scope of the Free Trade Agreement can contribute to an increase in the countries' trade volume and facilitate market access for both countries. In addition, thanks to the free trade agreement, it will be possible to increase trade in industrial products such as machinery and equipment and automotive parts. In addition, Free Trade Agreements to be signed between the two countries will allow the investment process between the two countries to accelerate. Ease of access to markets offered under Free Trade Agreements makes commercial investments attractive to investors, and this development leads to an increase in foreign direct investments. Additionally, a Free Trade Agreement between Uzbekistan and Turkey could create a more secure and predictable investment environment for businesspeople in both countries. With the ascension of Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Presidency in 2016, radical economic reforms were initiated in Uzbekistan in order to develop commercial activities between Türkiye and Uzbekistan. These reforms, carried out under Mirziyoyev's leadership, aim to transform Uzbekistan's economy into a more open and market-oriented structure. One of the main elements of the reforms is the liberalization of exchange rates. In 2017, strict controls on exchange rates in Uzbekistan were lifted, aligning the official exchange rate with the free market. This step created a more predictable business environment for both domestic and foreign investors and contributed to the revitalization of the country's foreign trade. Furthermore, this reform allowed Uzbekistan to improve its foreign trade balance and increase its exports. Another important pillar of economic reforms is the modernization of the tax system. Uzbekistan aimed to create a more efficient tax collection system by lowering tax rates and broadening the tax base. These improvements to the tax system increased the competitiveness of domestic businesses and helped reduce the informal economy. In addition, the Uzbekistan government has implemented a number of legal regulations to encourage foreign investments and improve the investment environment. Providing tax incentives for foreign investors and reducing bureaucracy has enabled an increase

in foreign direct investment inflows to the country. Thanks to these reforms, Uzbekistan's economic growth has accelerated and the country's integration into international trade networks has been strengthened [7]. The measures needed to increase trade between the two countries are not limited to these. In addition to these measures, great importance should also be given to developing political relations between the two countries. Recently, political relations between the two countries have been improving, and the two countries are becoming politically closer. This, in turn, has led to greater willingness to eliminate political barriers between them.

CONCLUSION

Foreign trade activities are extremely important for the development of national economies. Because foreign trade activities have important effects on macroeconomic variables. There is significant commercial potential between Türkiye and Uzbekistan, which have complementary economic structures. However, this potential could not be fully utilized due to some obstacles that existed between the two countries until recent years. These obstacles include geographical barriers (the two countries' distance from each other) and the resulting high transportation costs; the lengthy customs procedures; the lengthy and high cost of visa procedures; the lack of necessary facilities for Turkish investors; flaws in the tax system; and the failure of Uzbekistan to fully integrate into international trade due to the centrally planned economic model implemented during a certain period after its independence. Despite all these negativities, when the commercial activities between the two countries are examined over the years, it is seen that although exports and imports have followed a fluctuating course, they have generally shown an increasing trend. Political rapprochement between the two countries, particularly after 2020, and regulations designed to facilitate trade have been instrumental in increasing foreign trade activity. Furthermore, with Shavkat Mirziyoyev's ascension to the presidency in 2016, radical economic reforms were implemented in Uzbekistan, and as part of these reforms, exchange rates were liberalized and a more predictable business environment was created for foreign investors. In addition, the country's tax system has been modernized and the tax collection system has been improved, and a series of legal regulations have been implemented to encourage foreign investments. In this context, tax incentives provided for foreign investors and the reduction of bureaucracy have enabled an increase in foreign direct investment inflows to the country. Thanks to these reforms, Uzbekistan's economic growth has accelerated and the country's integration into international trade networks has been strengthened. The common goal of all these reforms is to transform the Uzbekistan economy into a more open and market-oriented structure and to ensure the development and sustainability of trade between the two countries.

In line with these objectives, signing Free Trade Agreements to develop trade between the two countries is of great importance. To increase trade between the parties through these Free Trade Agreements, trade barriers should be reduced or, if possible, eliminated. Furthermore, customs tariffs applied reciprocally by the two countries should be reduced or eliminated entirely, thereby reducing costs and increasing their trade volumes. In addition, mutual commercial investments should be made more attractive by facilitating investors' access to the market, thereby increasing foreign direct investment in both countries. Finally, the investment environment should be made safer and more predictable for business people in both countries through mutual guarantees and assurances.

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